

Agentification & the governance of European intellectual property rights: Competition, cooperation, and conflated agency governance

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This paper is part of a research project on The Governance of the European Patent System (PATGOV), funded by the European Commission (H2020/MSCA PATGOV 799203)

Presented at the TARN Conference “EU Agencies as ‘Inbetweeners’? The relationship between EU Agencies and Member States”, Maastricht, 4-5 December 2019

Abstract

This paper looks into two EU decentralized agencies that are involved in the management of intellectual property rights (IPRs), and that -to date- have been under-researched: (a) the European Union Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO) that deals with trademarks and industrial designs, and (b) the Community Plant Variety Office (CPVO) that deals with plant variety rights.

The paper first discusses the governance of IPRs in Europe (including patents, managed by a non-EU entity, the European Patent Office). Such governance is a balancing act between the need for unitary (i.e. EU-wide) protection as a cornerstone of the internal market, and the vested interests of national (often: centuries old) IP systems that provide limited territorial IP protection. European IP systems, and the (EU) agencies involved, to a large extent compete with national IP bodies, and at the same time need to cooperate with them, to create coordinated systems within the internal market. The main question the paper addresses is how this balancing act of coordination in a competitive environment affects the relationships between the various actors involved (and especially between national IP bodies and the EU agencies, EUIPO and CPVO), in terms of three dimensions of agency governance: control, network management and accountability.

The paper systematically discusses (a) competition (by analysing numbers of applications and market shares of IP offices, over time), (b) cooperation and coordination activities, and (c) the (formal) governance arrangements for the EUIPO and CPVO. It argues that these governance arrangements conflate and therefore do not adequately cover the three governance dimensions.

Keywords

European Union Intellectual Property Office, Community Plant Variety Office, agencies, intellectual property rights, European Patent Office, governance

Introduction

In the European Union (EU), two EU decentralized agencies are involved in the management of – specific- intellectual property rights (IPRs). The European Union Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO¹) deals with trademarks and industrial designs, and the Community Plant Variety Office (CPVO) deals with plant variety rights. Although these two agencies are (often) included, as cases, in research on EU agencies, dedicated research on the EUIPO and/or the CPVO is missing².

This stands in contrast to EUIPO's and CPVO's "big brother", the European Patent Organisation (EPOrg), an international organization (IO) of which all EU Member States are contracting parties, which has been researched quite well. More generally, compared to IPRs such as trademarks, designs and plant variety rights, the governance of patents (and to a lesser extent of copyrights), has been studied more extensively, and from various –disciplinary- angles (political science, law, public administration, economics, ethics, and science & technology studies). Many of the issues relevant to EU agentification (institutional hybridity, accountability, stakeholder involvement) have been discussed in the context of the EPOrg as well (e.g. Borrás 2006; Schneider 2009; Forsberg and Groenendijk 2019; Groenendijk 2016, 2019). These authors have concluded that the European patent system is a very closed system, a technocracy made up of legal and technical experts who at best interact with only those stakeholders directly involved in patenting practices (i.e. patent applicants) but hardly beyond the patent system as such (Kica & Groenendijk 2012). The system has distinct characteristics of a so-called epistemic community: a network of professionals with shared normative principles and beliefs, shared causal beliefs, a shared notion of what constitutes valid knowledge, and with a common policy enterprise (Haas 1992; Drahos 1999; Borrás 2006). The European Patent Office (EPOff, the EPOrg's secretariat/office that deals with the actual examination of applications and the granting of patents) has a high degree of autonomy and combines executive, quasi-judicial, and tacit legislative powers (Plomer 2019). This self-governance raises questions about transparency, accountability, democratic control and legitimacy (Schneider 2009; Borrás 2006; Borrás, Koutalakis & Wendler 2007).

This paper first and foremost provides a study of the EUIPO and CPVO, but the case of the EPOrg/EPOff serves as a point of reference throughout the paper, as it is relevant for various reasons. Firstly, although the EPOrg, as an IO separate from the EU, is not an EU agency, it has many structural

¹ Until March 2016: Office for Harmonization in the Internal Market (OHIM).

² An exception is the thick description by Fountain, Galinda-Dorado and Rothschild (2010) of the reform of the OHIM, prepared as a case study for educational purposes.

characteristics in common with EU agencies³. In IO literature, IOs such as the EPOrg, to which specific executive functions are delegated, are often viewed as a "complex agent", involving two principal-agent relations: one from the contracting parties to the IO as a whole, and one within the IO from the IO's supervisory body (made up of representatives from contracting parties) to the secretariat/executive office. This set-up is highly similar to that of EU agencies. Secondly, what the EPOrg, the EUIPO and the CPVO also have in common, is that they deal with the application of regulatory (IP-)frameworks in specific cases. Based on these frameworks, they take decisions that are binding to third parties. Thirdly, they are client-oriented agencies that are (almost) completely self-financed. Fourthly, they are all part of the same larger network of bodies (and people) that deal with IP rights, consisting of national IP offices and/or dedicated ministerial units, and global IP institutions such as the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). Fifthly, they all operate within in a highly competitive environment. Globally, the main regional IP offices (the "big five"⁴) compete on the quality of IP rights issued, the speed by which applications are processed, and the fees involved. Regionally, in the European case, there is competition between the European IP agencies and their national counterparts, as the dual European IP-system allows applicants for IPs to choose between a European application route and one or more national application route(s). Finally, rather than expanding the tasks of the EUIPO or establishing a new EU patent agency, the EPOff will be used ("borrowed") by the EU to implement the so-called unitary patent with unitary effect (UPUE, see section 2), in which case it will *de facto* be an agency of the EU.

Table 1: Main characteristics of European organizations involved in granting of intellectual property rights

<i>Organization</i>	<i>European Patent Organisation</i>	<i>Community Plant Variety Office</i>	<i>European Union Intellectual Property Office</i>
Acronym	EPOrg	CPVO	EUIPO
Type	International organization	EU agency	EU agency
Location(s)	Munich (DE), The Hague (NL), Berlin (DE), Vienna (AT)	Angers (FR)	Alicante (ES)
Established	1977	1994	1994
Operational since	1978	1995	1996
Maastricht pillar	(1 st)	1 st	1 st
Staff members (2018)	6.696	44	1.002
Annual budget (2018)	€ 2.4 billion	€ 16 million	€ 233 million
IPRs involved	Patent rights	Plant variety rights ⁵	Trademarks Designs (since 2003)

Sources: European Commission (2009), EU Agencies Network (2017), CPVO/EUIPO/EPO websites and reports

³ See also Borrás, Koutalakis and Wendler (2007), who compared (with a focus on input legitimacy) the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the European Medicines Agency (EMA), and the EPOrg/Off.

⁴ United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO); Japanese Patent Office (JPO); EPOrg; Korean Intellectual Property Office (KIPO); National Intellectual Property Administration of the People's Republic of China (CNIPA).

⁵ Or: plant breeders' rights.

Obviously, there are also important differences between on the EPORg/EPOff on the one hand and the EUIPO and CPVO on the other hand, beyond the obvious difference in formal status (IO versus EU agency). Firstly, sizes differ, as is shown in table 1. The EPORg involves 38 member states and thus reaches beyond the EU geographically. It is the third largest IO in the world, with about 6.700 staff. EUIPO has 1.000 staff and is the largest EU agency in staff size. The CPVO has only 44 staff and belongs to the smaller EU agencies. Secondly, patents have a much higher political salience than trademarks, designs, and plant variety rights. The patentability of inventions in specific areas such as stem cells, human embryos, and genetically modified organisms comes with contestation, as shown by fierce opposition from civil society/NGOs⁶. Criticism from the perspective of ethics is however not limited to such ‘patents-on-life’ issues. It also involves questions regarding broad and upstream product patents (that hinder rather than foster innovation), the importance of openness and of sharing of knowledge, specific health policy concerns arising from overpriced patented medicines, and the global justice dimension of patenting (Rigaud, 2008; Forsberg et al., 2018). Thirdly, as an IO the EPO enjoys immunity and is not governed by EU or by domestic regulations regarding budgetary control, transparency, or labour policy. Labour relations have been especially problematic at EPO over the last 10 years, linked to the coercive management style of Benoît Batistelli (EPOff-president from 2010-2018) (see also Forsberg & Groenendijk 2019). Financially, over the next decades the EPOff faces huge challenges in covering its pension payment obligations to (to-be) retired staff (Oliver Wyman/Mercer 2019).

The governance of IPRs in Europe is a balancing act between on the one hand the need for integration and unitary protection as a cornerstone of the internal market, and on the other hand the fact that national IPR systems are often centuries old and represent vested interests. European IPR systems engage in (vertical) competition with national IP bodies, which could be at odds with the need for integration and cooperation. *The main question the paper addresses is how this balancing act of coordination in a competitive environment affects the relationships between the various actors involved (and especially between national IP bodies and the EU agencies, EUIPO and CPVO), in terms of control, network management and accountability.*

The paper is structured as follows. In the next section, an overview is given of how various IPRs (patents, utility models, trade marks, plant variety rights, and industrial designs) are governed in the

⁶ See <https://www.no-patents-on-seeds.org/en/patent-cases> [Accessed 25.11.2019], for an overview of NGO-involvement in opposing the patentability of plants/animals.

EU. The subsequent sections focus on competition between the EUIPO/CPVO and national IP bodies, and on the cooperation dimension. The next section discusses the (formal) governance arrangements that are in place for EUIPO and CPVO. The final section concludes by means of a discussion of three dimensions of agency governance: control, network management, and accountability. It argues that that the formal governance arrangements conflate and therefore do not adequately cover these three governance dimensions.

IPRs and European integration

Intellectual property refers to creations of the mind and is commonly divided into two main categories: industrial property and copyright (WIPO 2011, p. 2). Industrial property refers to inventions and the use of symbols, names and images in a commercial context. Copyright covers literary works and artistic works. There are various detailed typologies of IPRs; here the most relevant IPRs are the following: (a) Patents and utility models; (b) Trade marks; (c) Plant variety rights; and (d) Industrial design rights⁷. How were these IPRs handled in the process of European integration and how are they currently governed?

Patents and utility models

In the context of European integration, patents were tackled first. A patent is an exclusive right granted for the protection of inventions (products or processes) offering a new technical solution or facilitating new ways of doing something (European IP Helpdesk 2019: 19).

A common system for patent rights was proposed already in 1949, within the Council of Europe (the so-called Longchambon plan, named after French senator Henri Longchambon). His idea was to set up a European Patent Office that would deal with registration of patent applications and examination of the main patentability elements (such as novelty and inventive step). National IP authorities would grant and administer the actual patents. A Committee of Experts of Patents (CEP), made up of representatives from national IP bodies, discussed the Longchambon plan. Two main elements for further study were identified (Partasarathy & Walker 2014). Firstly, there was the harmonisation of search and examination procedures and of patentability requirements and exclusions (given the huge differentials between the systems of the countries involved). Secondly, there was the question of how to organize the relationship between a European Patent Office (an agency *avant la lettre*) and the national IP bodies.

The CEP focused on the first issue in its Preliminary Comparative Study on Novelty and Patentability (April 1951). It went on to work on the basic harmonisation of substantive patent law, resulting first

⁷ Not discussed here, are: copyrights and related rights, geo-graphical indications, and trade secrets.

in the 1963 Strasbourg Convention on the Unification of Certain Points of Substantive Law on Patents for Invention, and later in the 1973 Munich Convention on the Grant of European Patents (or: European Patent Convention, EPC). Progress on this substantive harmonisation had been good enough to go one step further than the original Longchambon plan: the EPOff would not only register and examine applications, but would also grant the European patent, made up of a bundle of potential domestic patent rights, to be validated by national IP bodies in those countries that the applicant wants patent protection. The European route does not replace the national routes; it is still possible to apply on the domestic level, in which case national IP bodies deal with the whole process of registration, examination and granting of the patent. The governance structure (the second issue that the CEP looked at) followed from this division of tasks. The EPOrg has an Administrative Council (AC) made up of representatives of contracting states (one representative and one alternate each), that supervise the EPOff. Just as with the CEP itself, the AC of the EPOrg was and still is largely made up of heads of national IP bodies.

The EPOrg was thus conceived by the Council of Europe and its Member States, and the ground work was done before the Treaty of Rome was signed and before the start of the EEC. Whereas the main aim of the Council of Europe had been to create legal certainty for companies, the EEC approached the patent issue from the perspective of the core objective of the Treaty of Rome, the single market. It started to develop its own plans for a EEC patent system, i.e. it aimed for a unified EEC patent, centrally examined and granted, with immediate validity throughout the entire EEC territory. In 1962 a EEC Committee of Experts proposed such a single patent, also to be managed by a European Patent Office, with oversight by an Administrative Council made up of representatives from EEC Member States. It proposed that patent litigation for these EEC patents should also be unitary, and done by a specialised chamber of the European Court of Justice. Interestingly, this EEC Committee was made up of the same group of people (heads of national IP bodies) as the Council of Europe CEP, that proposed a non-unitary system.

The main strategic hurdle that the EEC had to take was the position of the United Kingdom. It was proposed that the EEC patent would be open to participation by non-EEC members, upon approval by the AC. Non-EEC members would be involved in the management of the European Patent Office, but could not be involved in the decision-making and legislation on the (EEC) patent system. For the United Kingdom this was acceptable only if it was a EEC member. If not, it preferred to have a common system of registration, examination and granting of the patent, but with validation (within the framework of their own patent law) on the domestic level for non-EEC (EFTA) members (and unitary for EEC members). After the negotiations on UK EEC membership broke down in 1963, and with the Council of Europe 1963 Strasbourg Convention in place, the case for such a two-tier system within the EEC framework lost momentum. An Intergovernmental Conference, made up of –again-

the heads of national IP bodies and a large group of observers, discussed all options and decided to go for the EPC/EPOrg option, even though the United Kingdom joined the EEC in 1973. The EPC was signed in 1973 and entered into force (in 1977) for a group of countries that was made up of six EEC Member States (Belgium, France, Germany, Luxembourg, the Netherlands and the newly joined United Kingdom) and one EFTA member (Switzerland; Sweden followed in 1978). It is an example of alternative integration, i.e. integration outside of the EU framework (Groenendijk 2007). It has been highly successful in terms of membership, going from seven contracting parties at the start to the current 38 contracting parties.

In addition to patent protection, some Member States⁸ have protection systems for utility models, sometimes called "petty patents". A utility model is an exclusive right granted for an invention, which allows its owner to prevent others from commercially using the protected invention, without their authorisation for a limited period of time. The requirements for a utility model (in terms of novelty and inventive step) are less strict than for a patent. Utility models are mainly used by SMEs, which is why some countries offer this type of low-threshold (and low-cost) protection. There is no European (or international) utility model protection, and no harmonisation has been undertaken in this field.

With the patent part of IPRs being brought outside of the EU framework, as a consolation prize, a unitary approach to IPRs was still possible in other fields, such as trademarks, plant variety rights, and industrial designs. Moreover, arguing from the perspective of a well-functioning single market, the EC has never given up on the idea of a unitary EU patent, which (58 years after it was first proposed) will probably come into effect in 2020 (see below).

Trademarks

A trade mark is an exclusive right over the use of a sign in relation to goods and services for which it is registered (European IP Helpdesk 2019: 5).

The Single European Act of 1986 triggered harmonisation of trade mark law, as disparities in trade mark law were considered to hamper the free movement of goods and the freedom to provide services, and were thought to distort competition. Basic harmonisation of trade mark law was put in place by means of the (first) Trademark Directive of 1989⁹. According to its pre-amble, full-scale

⁸ Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia and Spain.

⁹ First Council Directive to approximate the laws of the Member States relating to trade marks (89/104/EEC).

approximation was not necessary at that point of time, but the first Trade Mark Directive was rapidly followed by a second one¹⁰, which was amended over time and recast in 2015¹¹.

At the same time as the first Trade Mark Directive was conceived, preparations for a unitary trade mark began. Just as with patents, the choice was made to operate a dual system, in which a national route for protection co-existed with a European route, but with unitary protection. The first Community Trade Mark Regulation of 1994 introduced the Community Trade Mark (now called the EUTM)¹² and established the OHIM as an EU agency. The Regulation has been updated twice¹³. The relevant changes for the OHIM (including the name change to EUIPO) will be dealt with in sections 4 and 5.

Plant variety rights

Plant (and animal) varieties (including varieties developed by cross-breeding) are not patentable (for moral reasons), but the rights of plant breeders have to be protected. Plant variety rights prevent the free use by others of varieties developed by these breeders (Kiewiet 2005, p. 319). Plant variety rights holders can use and sell the variety as propagating material (and thus collect royalties). They are also entitled to the harvested materials resulting from the unauthorized use of their variety. Whereas all Member States had well-established trade mark systems, plant breeders protection has developed extensively in some Member States, but less so (or not at all) in other Member States. EU-wide harmonisation of plant variety protection was therefore not an issue. Instead, the Community Plant Variety System (CPVR) was established, in 1994, to be operated by CPVO¹⁴. The CPVR is the world's largest system of plant variety rights. Community plant variety rights are valid on the territory of the EU Member States, for 25 years for most species, and for 30 years for trees, wines and potatoes. The CPVR includes a Breeders' Exemption, which ensures that breeders can use protected varieties to create new varieties. Just as with the other IPRs, the system is dual: the CPVR offers EU wide protection, but national applications (with limited territorial validity) are still possible. Whereas the EPOff and the EUIPO cover the full process of registration, examination and granting of rights in their fields (patents, EU trademarks, and Registered Community designs), the CPVO depends on selected national offices for its examination.

¹⁰ Directive 2008/95/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council to approximate the laws of the Member States relating to trade marks.

¹¹ Directive (EU) 2015/2436 of the European Parliament and of the Council to approximate the laws of the Member States relating to trade marks (Recast).

¹² Council Regulation (EC) No 40/94 on the Community trade mark.

¹³ Council Regulation (EC) No 207/2009 on the European Union trade mark; Regulation (EU) 2017/1001 of the European Parliament and the Council on the European trade mark (codification).

¹⁴ Council Regulation (EC) No 2100/94 on Community plant variety rights.

Industrial designs

An industrial design is the outward appearance of the whole or part of a product resulting from the features of, in particular, the lines, contours, colours, shape, texture and/or materials of the product itself and/or its ornamentation (European IP Helpdesk 2019: 13).

The path taken here is very similar to the approach to trade marks. Firstly, there has been harmonisation of national systems through a Design Directive of 1998¹⁵, which has not been changed since. Secondly, there is the Design Regulation of 2002, which introduced the Registered Community Design (RCD)¹⁶, to be managed by OHIM/EUIPO (since 2003). To be eligible for a RCD a design has to be aesthetic, novel and have an individual character. The RCD procedure is however fairly light and centres around registration, without extensive substantive examination of prior rights. The RCD offers EU wide protection. Just as with trade marks, the RCD possibility is additional to national design protection.

¹⁵ Directive 98/71/EC of the European Parliament and the Council on the legal protection of designs.

¹⁶ Council Regulation (EC) No 6/2002 on Community Designs. This Regulation also introduced the UCD (Unregistered Community Design), for which no registration is needed. Protection is obtained automatically for a period of three years from the design's first public disclosure within the EU. The UCD offers a slightly weaker right than a RCD.

The unitary patent

In 1975 (two years after the EPC was signed) the –then- nine Member States of the EEC (the six founding countries and Denmark, Ireland and the United Kingdom) also signed the Community Patent Convention¹⁷ (Pitkethly, 1999), which never entered into force. After decades of negotiations, an agreement on unitary patent protection was however reached in 2012¹⁸. The UP (formally: the European patent with unitary effect, UPUE) is the result of an enhanced cooperation scheme (based on Article 20 TEU, Articles 326-334 TFEU), in which 26 EU Member States are involved (Spain and Croatia are out). The start of this new system is expected for the first half of 2020. Linked to the UP is the establishment of the Unified Patent Court (UPC), agreed upon in 2013¹⁹. Here, in addition to Spain and Croatia, Poland does not participate. The position of the United Kingdom, although it has ratified the UPC agreement in 2018, is unclear as UPC-participation depends on a UK-EU Brexit deal being in place. More generally, the uncertainties surrounding Brexit have led to ratification delays in some countries, most notably Germany.

Registration, examination and granting of UPUE applications will be done by the EPOff²⁰, but the UPUE puts an end to a number of disadvantages of regular EPC patents. First, as opposed to the EPC patents, validation in individual Member States is no longer required. An additional advantage is that an application can be made in English, German or French (just as with EPO patents), but granted UPUEs do not have to be translated in all official EU languages; with EPC patents such translation is still required for validation purposes. Secondly, patent litigation will take place on the EU level as well, through the UPC.

Table 2: Regulatory frameworks for main IPRs in Europe

IPRs	Harmonisation of national IP law?	Unitary IP?	Unitary IP managed by ...
Patents	EPC, TRIPS, Biotech Directive	UPUE (2020)	EPOff
Utility models	-	-	-
Trade marks	Trade mark Directives	EUTM	EUIPO
Plant variety rights	-	CPVR	CPVO
Industrial designs	Design Directive	RCD, UCD	EUIPO

¹⁷ Convention for the European Patent for the Common Market (76/76/EEC).

¹⁸ Regulation (EU) No 1257/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council implementing enhanced cooperation in the area of the creation of unitary patent protection; Council regulation (EU) No 1260/2012 implementing enhanced cooperation in the area of the creation of unitary patent protection with regard to the applicable translation arrangements.

¹⁹ Agreement on a unified patent court, signed on 19 february 2013.

²⁰ To that end the EU Member States have established a common system of patents for Parties in the EPC, an enhanced cooperation procedure that the EPC allows for (Art. 142 EPC).

Recap: regulatory frameworks for IPRs in Europe

Table 2 summarizes the current situation in terms of regulation of IPRs in Europe.

What has not been mentioned above is that regarding patents harmonisation of national patent law has not only taken place through the 1973 EPC (revised in 2000), but also through global frameworks such as the WHO Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS). In addition, there is the 1998 EU Biotech Directive²¹, which puts limits on the patentability of some biotech inventions, for ethical reasons. The content of the Biotech Directive was implemented into the EPC and the EPC's Implementing Rules, and thus became relevant for non-EU EPC countries as well.

IPR protection in Europe and globally

To finalize this section, table 3 shows the various possibilities there are to acquire IP protection. Not included in the overview, and not discussed above, are the international routes in addition to the national and European routes, through WIPO and through the International Union for the Protection of New Varieties of Plants (UPOV). In most cases such international applications are initially handled through registration by national IP bodies. Patents, trade marks, and industrial designs handled by WIPO, as well as plant variety rights handled by UPOV, also still have to be validated on the domestic level before the protection takes effect. As the disparities between IPR law are generally large (given the large group of contracting states involved²²), validation of rights granted by WIPO and/or UPOV is not always successful.

²¹ Directive 98/44/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on the legal protection of biotechnological inventions.

²² WIPO patents can be validated in up to 150 states, WIPO trade marks (through the so-called Madrid system) in up to 100 states, and WIPO industrial designs (through the so-called The Hague system) in up to 65 states. UPOV plant variety rights can be validated in up to 76 states.

Table 3: Current (European) possibilities ('routes') to obtain IP protection, for various types of IP rights

IPR	National (single state)	European	(Initial) protection period
Patents	Registration, examination and granting: national	(1)-Registration, examination and granting of EPC patent by EPOff Protection after validation: national (up to 38 states) (2)-Registration, examination, and granting of unitary patent (UPUE) by EPOff Protection after validation: almost EU-wide (27 EU MSs)	20 years
Utility models	Registration, examination and granting: national (in 50% of the EU Member States ²³)	-	7-10 years
Trade marks	Registration, examination and granting: national	Registration: EUIPO (EUTM) Protection: EU	10 years
Industrial designs	Registration, examination and granting: national	Registration: EUIPO (RCD) Protection: EU	5 years
Plant variety rights	Registration, examination and granting: national (24 EU Member States ²⁴)	Registration: CPVO Protection: EU (CPVR)	25-30 years

Sources: European IP Helpdesk (2018, 2019)

Competition for applications

In his early analysis of the establishment of EU agencies like OHIM and CPVO, Kreher (1997, p. 240) remarked that national authorities would certainly face competition by these new agencies. In the pre-ambles of the relevant Regulations such competition is also acknowledged. What has been the impact of the introduction of unitary protection schemes such as the EUTM, the RCD and the CPVR on application behaviour?

As explained in the previous section, in the dual systems that the EUIPO and CPVO operate in, applicants can choose between national routes and the EU route, for protection of their trade marks, industrial designs or plant varieties. Various considerations may play a role in this choice, such as the application (and renewal) fees, the speed by which applications are handled, the potential a granted right has for validation (domestic or unitary), and the quality of the granted right (will it be enforceable in court?). Additionally, other factors may be relevant such as the possibility to apply in one's own language²⁵, the geographical proximity of the handling office, the availability of on-line

²³ Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia and Spain. The other EU Member States do not use utility models in their IP systems.

²⁴ Cyprus, Greece, Luxembourg and Malta do not have a system of plant variety protection.

²⁵ This issue is however of minimal relevance as at CPVO and EUIPO applications can be made in all EU official languages. Internally, the EUIPO uses five working languages (English, French, German, Italian and Spanish); in CPVO the working language is English.

search engines for prior art, and the possibility to apply on-line. National IP bodies and the EUIPO/CPVO compete on all these factors.

Figure 1A and 1B show the development of *applications for trade marks* (in absolute numbers and in shares) received by national IP bodies and the EUIPO, for the period 1994-2018; the EUTM has been operational since 1996. It is clear that the EUTM was an instant success; it received 43.144 applications in its first year. Applications have increased in the period 1997-2009, although in a slightly volatile matter; since 2009 the increase is more steady. The current market share of the EUIPO is 22%. Germany, France and Italy have been able to withstand the competition. Especially over the last five years, the UK has become another important player. The Benelux Office for Intellectual Property (BIOP), a regional office, shows a decreasing share; in all likelihood, applicants find it relatively easy to switch from such a regional office to the EUIPO.

The number of applications for the EUTM at OHIM/EIUPPO thus exceeded all expectations. The then assistant to the OHIM president, Paul Maier recalls that OHIM had counted on 15.000 applications, to be handled by appr. 250 staff members. Capacity turned out to be much too low, and all hands were on deck, with even the OHIM President opening application letters. Facilities were insufficient, resulting in the frequent use of fax machines at a local grocery store and at the Mayor's Office in Alicante²⁶.

²⁶ Interview findings from Fountain, Galinda-Dorado and Rothschild (2010, p. 4).

Figure 1A

Figure 1B

Tables 2A and 2B provide similar information for *applications for plant variety rights*, for the period 1996-2017 (with data for applications at national plant variety bodies missing for 2002-2010). Here a similar picture emerges. The CPVO received 1.378 applications in its first full year in operation (1996), instantly outperforming its main rival, the Netherlands. The CPVO currently has a market share of 70%; the Netherlands has a market share of 16% (compared to 21% in 1996). National applications in other Member States have been reduced to insignificant levels. The UK is the only country where application numbers have recently picked up. This resembles the development for trade marks, and could signal an anticipation effect of Brexit.

Figure 2A

Figure 2B

Figure 3A

Finally, figures 3A and 3B deal with *applications for industrial designs*, for the period 2003-2018. The development corresponds fully to the other cases. The EUIPO received 10.412 applications for

industrial designs in the first year (2003), and the number (as well as the EUIPO’s market share) has been increasing ever since. The EUIPO’s market share is now 56%. Other important players are Germany, France and the United Kingdom; again, the data for the United Kingdom show an upward movement in recent years.

Figure 3B

As stated above, many factors can play a role in the applicant’s decision to go for the unitary route or the national route. Some research has been done on what the main determining factors are, in the case of trade marks and industrial designs (Max Planck Institute 2011; European Commission 2016). Fees at the EUIPO are generally higher than at national IP offices, but the variety in national fee levels is high. Whether it is cheaper to go for a unitary right, or to apply nationally will thus depend on the (series of) national right(s) involved. Roughly, the unitary route becomes relatively less costly, the larger the number of countries is in which protection is sought. Not surprisingly, the national route is favoured more by SMEs, whereas the unitary route is favoured more by larger companies. This also indicates some sort of specialisation between national IP bodies and the EUIPO.

Application fees do not cover the full transaction costs of application; these also include the costs of actual application, which are generally higher in the case of multiple applications (in different languages) at the national level. It is also important to point out that only a small share of applications is made by companies themselves. Estimates are that 60-90% of the applications at EUIPO are done by specialized intermediaries/agents. These agents often base their fee on the

application fee, but they use higher charge ratios for national applications (which involve more time) than for EUIPO applications.

Generally, ease of applying, speed of processing and service quality are important factors, and may explain much of the success of OHIM/EUIPO. From its start, and especially after the first years of coping with an unexpected high workload, the EUIPO decided to become a paperless office and to go for full on-line communication with its applicants (Fountain, Galindo-Dorado & Rotschild 2010).

Whereas many national IP offices struggled to implement ICT in their (internal and external) processes, the EUIPO has been very successful in doing so. As a new office, it was not constrained by path-dependency in its primary processes. Moreover, the scale on which it is operated made it possible to set the standard in the use of IT systems. This was also encouraged by the EC. Commissioner McCreevy, in 2008, endorsed the ambition of the EUIPO to be the benchmark amongst industrial property offices²⁷.

At the CPVO a similar development can be discerned. Although the CPVO is a much smaller agency, it too has paid considerable attention to the use of ICT in its processes, from the early years on.

To conclude, right from the introduction of the unitary trade mark, the CPVR and –later- the RCD, the OHIM/EUIPO and CPVO have been able to establish themselves as market leaders in their fields, especially by means of providing ICT-backed services to applicants. Only the larger national IP offices have been able to maintain their position. A division of tasks (or of target groups) has developed, with national IP offices targeting SMEs and the two EU agencies targeting larger companies.

Cooperation

In this section an overview is given of how the EUIPO and the CPVO cooperate with their counterparts at the national level. Prior to that, the main drivers of such cooperation are discussed.

Drivers of cooperation: harmonisation, systems competition and task expansion

National IP bodies have been confronted with three mutually reinforcing developments. Firstly, as outlined in section 2, there has been substantial harmonisation in these two fields (but has been absent in the case of plant variety rights), both regarding substantive law and procedures. Such harmonisation explicitly targets the Member States, and follows the logic of coercion and compliance as one of the three governance patterns in EU regulatory policy as distinguished by Knill & Lenschow (2015). Especially harmonisation of registration procedures has created a need to cooperate between these national IP bodies and with OHIM/EUIPO. Interestingly, the latest Trade Mark

²⁷ OHIM, Annual Report (2008, p. 29).

Directive explicitly addresses such cooperation, both in its preamble and in Article 51, in order to promote convergence of practices and tools in relation to the examination and registration of trade marks. Secondly, with the establishment of unitary trade marks, industrial designs and plant variety rights, systems competition (the second regulatory governance mode of Knill & Lenschow) has increased. In a harmonised environment, such competition cannot take place through divergence, but often leads to convergence by means of yardstick competition and peer pressure, in a cooperative context (mutual learning, exchange of best practices). Thirdly, the tasks of the EUIPO and the CPVO have expanded over the last two decades. In the earlier literature, they were often depicted as EU agencies with a straightforward and unidimensional task, as executive agencies, applying detailed law in single cases (Kreher 1997), or as adjudicational agencies (Everson 1995). Moreover, some have pointed to the fact that the EUIPO and CPVO are not full regulatory agencies, as they are not involved in enforcement, which in the case of IPRs falls on the holders of these rights (Scott, 2015). In reality, they –currently- cover a much wider range of functions, and are involved in communication and information exchange in networks (the third mode of Knill & Lenschow), as well as in the development of soft law by means of guidelines (Rocca and Eliantonio 2019), and in infringement issues. Especially in the case of EUIPO, this task expansion has been driven by updates of its formal mandate.

CPVO

In its Strategic Plan 2017-2021 the CPVO mentions two strategic goals: (a) making plant variety rights the natural choice for the protection of IP related to plant varieties²⁸, and (b) being an innovative, people-driven organisation promoting EU values. Its main current focus (apart from adequately managing the CPVR and serving plant breeders) seems to be to enhance the awareness and status of plant variety rights in the IP world at large. In the Strategic Plan 2017-2021 two related strategic activities are mentioned: making the CPVO strong in a strong IP network, and promoting plant variety rights both in the EU and internationally. According to Woods (2018) this focus on awareness and relevance in the IP world has been promoted –informally- by the EC.

In light of this broad orientation, and given the absence of harmonisation in the field of plant variety rights, cooperation between the CPVO and national plant variety protection offices is rather limited. The CPVO Strategic Plan 2017-2021 mentions these national PVP offices just once (they are not even mentioned as stakeholders of CPVO). The CPVO mainly cooperates with national examination offices

²⁸ This must be seen in the light of developments in biotechnology concerning genetic engineering of plant varieties, and the potential use of patents rather than conventional plant variety rights for IP protection. See Holthuis & Van der Velden (2019) for more details.

(and experts). The CPVO does not own any technical infrastructure itself, and needs these offices to assist in the technical assessment of candidate varieties for the CPVR. Based on common technical protocols, these examination offices determine whether a variety is distinct, uniform and stable (the so-called DUS test). The CPVO Administrative Council has to consent with the use by the CPVO of such national examination offices (article 30(4) CPVR Regulation). These examination offices are not (necessarily) the same bodies that on the national level decide on applications for plant variety rights²⁹. There are 26 of such national technical examination offices in the EU; not all Member States have such specialized bodies and some countries have more than one (Italy: 3; Denmark, Belgium, United Kingdom: 2). In addition, there are technical examination offices that the CPVO uses in non-EU countries (Australia, Israel, Japan, Mexico, New Zealand, South Africa, Taiwan).

The CPVO website also lists the following (international) partners, which represent their main stakeholders (plant breeders)³⁰: International Association of Horticultural Producers (AIPH, located in the United Kingdom); International community of breeders of asexually reproduced ornamental and fruit-tree varieties (CIOFORA, located in Germany), European Seed Association (ESA, located in Belgium), International Seed Federation (ISF, located in Switzerland), International Society of Horticultural Science (ISHS, located in Belgium), and the International Seed Testing Association (ISTA, located in Switzerland).

The CPVO cooperates with EUIPO in the framework of the European Observatory on infringements of intellectual property rights (see below); to that end it has set up a case law database of judgments on plant variety rights infringements. In addition, the CPVO cooperates closely with the global IP-organization that deals with plant variety rights, the International Union for the Protection of New Varieties of Plants (UPOV, located in Switzerland).

EUIPO

The three drivers for cooperation outlined earlier in this section, are all very relevant for the case of the EUIPO. Trade mark and industrial design law have been substantially harmonised, through its success with the EUTM and RCD the EUIPO into a benchmark, market leader and central player, and its tasks have been expanded considerably. In its Strategic Plan 2025 the EUIPO fully acknowledges its responsibility for cooperation activities within the two-tier European trade mark and design systems based on the principles of coexistence and complementarity. Currently, according to the 2017 Trademark regulation, the main tasks of the –renamed- EUIPO are as follows:

²⁹ For example, in the Netherlands plant variety rights are issued by the *Raad voor plantenrassen* (Board for Plant Varieties, a so-called Autonomous Public Authority (APA, or agency). Technical examinations are done by *Naktuinbouw*, another APA.

³⁰ <https://cpvo.europa.eu/en/about-us/who-we-are/network-of-partners#zoom=4&lat=54.29088&lon=13.18359&layers=TB> [Accessed 17.11.2019]

- Management of the EU trademark and design systems (its core tasks);
- To promote convergence of practices and tools in the fields of trademarks and designs in cooperation with national IP offices of the EU Member States, including the BOIP. This cooperation task is mirrored by a similar stipulation in the 2015 Trademark Directive for national IP offices and the BIOP;
- To manage the online EU-wide database for Orphan Works;
- To run the European Observatory on Infringements of Intellectual Property Rights.

The Trademark Regulation explicitly states that for all these tasks the EUIPO shall cooperate widely. The work of the EUIPO thus extends beyond registration, and includes harmonisation of registration practices and the development of common IP management tools, in cooperation with the national and regional IP offices throughout EU-28, user associations and other institutional partners. The objective is to offer users of EUTMs and RCDs a similar registration experience, be it at the national or at the EU level. Such cooperation is not new. In the late 1990s the OHIM already reached out to IP offices (often: *in statu nascendi*) of accession states, in light of the 2004 and 2007 enlargements. Moreover, since 2010 structured cooperation was enabled by the so-called Cooperation Fund (financed by the OHIM's budgetary surplus, involving € 50 mln), later complemented by a program (with specific projects) for convergence of practices between the OHIM and national IP offices and BOIP (Convergence Programme). These efforts focused on areas such as the development of common examination standards, the creation of common or connected databases and portals, the exchange of data and information, the establishment of common standards and practices, and the exchange of technical expertise. This cooperation turned into the European Trade Mark and Design Network (ETMDN), a hub, run by EUIPO, that connects national and regional IP offices, user associations and other IP organizations, working together to achieve a harmonized trademark and design system in Europe. After the 2017 Trademark Regulation became effective, this network was re-labelled the European Union Intellectual Property Network (EUIPN). It is funded by the EUIPO, for up to 15% of its annual revenue. The development of existing cooperation into such a European IP network had been an earlier strategic objective of EUIPO (Strategic Plan 2020), just as the establishment of the ETMDN was a main objective of the Strategic Plan 2011-2015³¹.

The EUIPO is also responsible for maintaining an Orphan Works registry, as part of the Orphan Works Directive³². This directive creates a legal framework to facilitate the digitisation and dissemination of works and other subject matter which are protected by copyright or related rights

³¹ Levi-Faur (2011) distinguishes between three types of institutionalization of agencies: agentification (i.e. agencies replacing existing networks), agencified networks (i.e. agencies competing with other networks), and networking agencies (i.e. agencies that create networks). Clearly, the EUIPO is such a networking agency.

³² Directive 2012/28/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on certain permitted uses of orphan works.

and for which no rightholder is identified or for which the rightholder, even if identified, is not located (so-called orphan works). The directive explicitly outlines the cooperation obligations Member States and the EUIPO have. The fact that this task refers to copyrights, and not to trade marks and industrial designs, was the main reason behind the name change from OHIM to EUIPO. Since 2012, EUIPO also hosts the European Observatory on Infringements of Intellectual Property Rights, which brings together public and private stakeholders in the fight against piracy and counterfeiting³³.

Internationally, EUIPO cooperates with the EPO and WIPO, and with IP offices in non-EU countries.

EUIPO AND CPVO: governance arrangements

It is important to point out that the OHIM and CPVO did not have any institutional or procedural frontrunners (Kreher 1997). In that sense they differ from most EU agencies, that replaced existing comitology arrangements and/or scientific and advisory committees (Vos 2018).

Based on an analysis of the relevant regulations and EUIPO and CPVO websites, table 4 lists the main governance arrangements. Given that the most recent Trademark Regulation is from 2017, and the CPVR Regulation is from 1994, some differences between the EUIPO and CPVO occur. These mainly refer to the terminology and to the position of the EC and EP (CPVO: no representation of EP, no voting rights for the EC).

³³ Regulation (EU) No 386/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council on entrusting the Office for Harmonization in the Internal Market (Trade Marks and Designs) with tasks related to the enforcement of intellectual property rights, including the assembling of public and private-sector representatives as a European Observatory on Infringements of Intellectual Property Rights.

Table 4: General governance arrangements for the EUIPO and CPVO

Organization	EUIPO	CPVO
Board(s)	Management Board & Budget Committee Boards of Appeal	Administrative Council Boards of Appeal
MB&BC/AC members	28 from MSs; 2 from EC; 1 from EP	28 from MSs; 1 from EC
MB&BC/AC members term	Unlimited	Unlimited
Alternates	Yes	Yes
Voting rights in MB&BC/AC	MSs, EC, EP	MSs
Default decision rule in MB&BC/AC	Simple majority	Simple majority
Qualified majority	QM of 2/3 for adoption of the annual work programme, adoption of multiannual strategic programme, election of MB/BC chair, adoption of lists of candidates for position of executive director and presidents/chair Board of Appeal, adoption of the budget, adoption of internal financial provisions	QM of 3/4, for decisions on compulsory licensing, general guidelines, management report, rules for working methods, test guidelines, disciplinary authority over senior officials, appointment of members of Boards of Appeal, adoption of the budget, adoption of internal financial provisions
Chair & deputy chair MB&BC/AC	Chair and deputy chair chosen from among MB members; 4 years, renewable once	Chair and deputy chair AC chosen from among AC members; 3 years, renewable
Management of the Office	Executive Director Appointed by the Council, list of candidates proposed by MB Term: 5 years, renewable once Removal from office by the Council acting on a proposal by the MB	President of the Office Appointed by the Council, list of candidates proposed by Commission after obtaining the opinion of the AC Term: 5 years, renewable Dismissal by the Council acting on a proposal by the Commission, after obtaining the opinion of the AC
Presidents/chairs Boards of Appeal	Cf. procedure for executive director; removal from office after Court of Justice decision	Cf., procedure for President of the Office; removal from office after Court of Justice decision
Observers in MB&BC/AC	Permanent observers: WIPO, BIOP, EPO, CPVO, INTA, BUSINESSEUROPE, Marques, Acta, AIM Rotating observers: APRAM, AIPPI, CNIPA, EURATEX, FICPI, GRUR, ICC, CITMA, LESI, UNION	Ciopora, European Seeds Association, Plantum (plant breeders' organisations)

Sources: 2017 Trademark Regulation; 1994 CPVR Regulation, EUIPO and CPVO websites and most recent annual reports

An important issue regarding representation in EU agencies has always been the background of MB/AC members, and the question whether they represent the political-administrative bodies (ministries) or come from national agencies (see the literature review in Egeberg & Trondal 2011). Table 5 lists the origin of the current AC members of the CPVO. Here the composition is quite mixed. There is no representation from ministries of economic affairs, and limited representation from national IP offices. Apparently, the CPVR is primarily thought of as an instrument in the food (safety)

and agricultural domain, and not such much as an IPR. The EC representative is from DG SANTE (Director Crisis management in food, animals and plants).

Table 5: Origins of AC members CPVO (primary representatives, not alternates)

Ministry (agriculture, food, environment)	11x	Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, France, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Malta, Netherlands, Portugal, Slovenia
Agency for health & food (safety)	5x	Austria, Denmark, Finland, Sweden, UK ³⁴
Specialized (plant variety) agency	6x	Estonia, Germany, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Latvia, Spain
Test/examination institute	4x	Czech Republic, Poland, Romania, Slovakia
National IP office	2x	Belgium, Italy

Source: CPVO website

Table 6 shows similar information for the composition of the MB of the EUIPO.

Table 6: Origins of MB members EUIPO (primary representatives, not alternates)

Ministry (economic affairs)	5x	Belgium, Cyprus, Greece, Malta, Netherlands
Ministry (justice)	1x	Germany
Ministry (foreign affairs)	1x	Italy
National IP office	21x	Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Hungary, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom

Source: EUIPO website

Here we have a different picture. Most representatives are from national IP bodies. The (two) EC representatives are from DG Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs. No information was provided on the EP representative.

As the EUIPO also has a Budgetary Committee, we would expect the composition of that BC to be different from that of the MB, for reasons of specialization. Table 7 shows that that is not really the case. Even though there are some differences, the overall composition is the same, with a majority of members coming from national IP bodies. Interestingly, in 40% of the cases (11 persons) the MB member is the same as the BC member. In 40% of the cases (11 persons), the MB and BC member are different, in 20% of the cases (6 persons) the alternate MB is the first representative in the BC. The EC representatives are the same persons. Given these similarities in composition, and given that the EUIPO MB and BC often meet at the same time and/or jointly, one can question the rationale for having two boards.

³⁴ The UK representative is from Fera Science Limited, formerly the Food and Environment Research Agency, now a joint venture based in the United Kingdom owned by Capita (a business processes outsourcing company, 75%) and the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs (DEFRA) (25%).

Table 7: Origins of MB members EUIPO (primary representatives, not alternates)

Ministry (economic affairs)	5x	Cyprus, Greece, Italy, Malta, Netherlands
Ministry (justice)	1x	Germany
National IP office	22x	Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Hungary, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom

Source: EUIPO website

In addition to the overview on cooperation activities in the previous section, some more formal arrangements on stakeholder involvement can be discussed. Stakeholder involvement in the EUIPO and CPVO is arranged primarily through observers in the MB&BC/AC (see table 4). A major difference is the limited use of observers by CPVO compared to the extensive use by the EUIPO. The EUIPO also has a very large user group, consisting of 23 organisations, some of them also represented as observers in the MB&BC. It organises public consultations on specific cooperation projects, and on its Strategic Plan. Its website is fully up to standards in terms of transparency and access to documents. The CPVO also arranges regular consultations, for specific projects and its Strategic Plan. It cooperates with a –limited- group of users/plan breeders associations (see previous section), two of which (Ciopora, ESA) also have observer status in the AC.

Finally, table 8 lists the main elements of the financial governance arrangement for both agencies.

Table 8: Financial governance arrangements for the EUIPO and CPVO

Budget proposal	Executive Director	President
Budget adoption	BC (qualified majority)	AC (qualified majority)
Execution of budget	Executive Director	President
External budgetary control	European Court of Auditors	European Court of Auditors
Discharge	BC (simple majority)	AC (simple majority)
Fees set by	2017 Trademark regulation (annex I) Commission Regulation (CRD)	Commission Regulation

Sources: 2017 Trademark Regulation; 1994 CPVR Regulation, EUIPO and CPVO websites and most recent annual reports

These financial arrangements are standard for the EU agencies that were established in the 1990s. The OHIM and CPVO have adopted their own financial regulations (after consultation of the EC and the European Court of Auditors), performs its own audit and control, and –as all agencies- are subject to external ex post budgetary control by the European Court of Auditors. The EUIPO and CPVO are however special in the sense that they are not funded out of the EU budget, but by user fees (as is also stipulated in the relevant Regulations). Without going into much detail (as the fee structure of especially trade mark applications is quite complicated), in practice both the EUIPO and the CPVO

have generated considerable ex post budget surpluses³⁵, even though ex ante their budgets must be balanced. Given the competition between the EUIPO/CPVO and national IP offices, such surpluses have not been received well by MB&BC/AC members, who perceived the agencies as making profits at the expense of national IP bodies. Similarly, users prefer cost-efficient fees³⁶. In the early years fees could be set by the agencies themselves, but this has changed. The EC, as a party independent from both the EUIPO/CPVO and the national offices, sets the fees through implementing regulations (for trade mark applications this has however been done in the 2017 Trademark Regulation itself). Moreover, in the case of EUIPO, cooperation activities are financed by the EU agencies (as was done earlier through the Cooperation Fund of OHIM), for up to 15% of the agency budget. In addition, EUIPO shall offset on a yearly basis the costs incurred to national IP offices/BIPO and other relevant authorities in carrying out tasks stemming from the implementation of the EU trademark. This involves opposition and invalidation procedures involving EU trademarks, enforcement activities (including counterfeit goods in transit) and information on the EU trademark system. The offset corresponds to 5% of annual revenue of the EUIPO (which can be increased to 10% in case of large budgetary surpluses, upon suggestion by EUIPO, approved by its MB&BC). EUIPO is not obliged to this offset in a given year if they suffer an (ex post) budgetary deficit. Distribution of the offset to Member States is done by means of a key with four indicators (one of them being the annual number of EU trademark applications originating from applicants in that MS). If there is an ex post budgetary surplus for five consecutive years, the BC (upon proposal of Office) can decide to transfer the surplus to the general budget of the EU.

Discussion and conclusion: three dimensions of agency governance

The EUIPO and the CPVO operate in a mixed environment of competition and cooperation. In this final and concluding section, the governance arrangements are assessed by focusing on three dimensions of agency governance: control, network management and accountability. First, the importance of distinguishing between these three elements of agency governance is outlined and underpinned. Secondly, by going through these dimensions one for one, the section will argue that these arrangements conflate and therefore do not adequately cover the three governance dimensions.

³⁵ See "The EU agency that has too much money", EUObserver, 21 March 2016, <https://euobserver.com/institutional/132723> [Accessed 25.11.2019].

³⁶ However, intermediaries, who base their fee on the fees agencies charge, do not necessarily have a preference for lower fees, as this negatively impacts their business model.

Three dimensions of EU agency governance: control, network management and accountability

In agentification and IO literature, governance of agencies is often framed as a *control* issue, within a principal-agent framework. Delegation (either for efficiency or for credibility) by a principal to an agent, results in an agency problem, given differences in preferences between principal and agent, and information asymmetries (see for example Groenendijk 1997, 2019). The more discretion (or: autonomy) the agent has, the more likely it is that the agent's actions result in outcomes that do not reflect principal's preferences. These potential welfare losses for the principal provide an incentive to engage in monitoring and control efforts. Likewise, the agent, who will suffer a welfare loss due to control by the principal, will engage in efforts to keep the principal at bay. Monitoring (oversight) is needed to overcome the information asymmetry. Based on this, the principal has two options to interfere: (a) decrease the level of discretion/autonomy, (b) tease the agent into desired actions by means of budgetary incentives. In the case of the EUTM, the RCD and the CPVR, the main principal is the Council, with the EUIPO and the CPVO as agents. Adequate control by the principal of these agents is the first element of agency governance.

Given the entanglement of EU agencies and national counterparts, another frame is that of *network management*. This governance dimension is not based on a delegation logic, but on a cooperation logic. It is about adequately involving all relevant cooperation actors, both in terms of interests and in terms of the resources they bring to the network (pooling, see Egeberg & Trondal 2017).

The third frame is *accountability*. Accountability is not about delegation, but about giving account on the organization's mandate, to various fora of interested parties, i.e. societal groups, who have an interest in the way the mandate is performed, because they are impacted by that. They are parties that have a "stake" in the organization's actions (stakeholders), but do not necessarily contribute to these actions.

Unfortunately, accountability and control are sometimes conflated; ex post oversight or budgetary control mechanisms are then presented as accountability mechanisms (see e.g. Lehouste 2008; Busuioc 2009; Sauer 2011; Vos 2014; Buess 2014). For example, the external budgetary control of agencies by the European Court of Auditors (ECA) is not about accountability, as the ECA is not a stakeholder. The ECA is an agent that performs monitoring activities on other agents (such as the Commission and EU agencies), on behalf of a principal (Council/European Parliament).

Another common mix-up is that of 'stakeholder' involvement and accountability. Involvement of a network partner, for example of users/clients through advisory committees or consultations is a matter of management (i.e. bringing their interests and expertise into the network), not an accountability mechanism.

Control

From the perspective of delegation, and principal-agent control, the Trademark regulation, the RCD Regulation and the CPVR Regulation determine the basic level of autonomy of the agent. The principal here is the legislator, i.e. Council (together with EP, for the more recent Trademark Regulation). The agent is the Executive Director/President, who is appointed by the principal. From the perspective of the principal, this agent is supposed to take decisions on applications for IPRs according to the preferences of the principal, but the agent can drift away from these preferences. The principal has a number of instruments at his disposal to control the agent. First, there are *oversight mechanisms*. In the EUIPO/CPVO set-up, oversight is however not done by the principal, but by the MB&BC/AC through their involvement in for example the adoption of annual reports and the discharge for budget execution. Such delegation of oversight by principals is not uncommon, but in this case there is no direct delegation link or contract between the Council and MB&BC/AC members, and, as was shown above, they do not represent the political perspective regarding IPRs. In all likelihood it is the EC that safeguards this perspective, if it is safeguarded at all in the MB&BC/AC. Another oversight mechanism is the ex post external budgetary control by the European Court of Auditors, but that oversight has a limited scope. The built-in judicial review by means of Boards of Appeal (and potential follow-up by the Court of Justice) can be considered to be another oversight mechanism, with appointment of the President and chairs of these boards by the Council. Secondly, as explained above, a principal can control the agent by means of *budgetary incentives*. As the EUIPO and CPVO are financed by user fees, there is no budgetary contract between the Council and the agencies, which makes it impossible to use such incentives. Thirdly, control can be executed by means of *limiting the discretion* an agent has, through additional rules that guide the agents behaviour. The adoption by the MB&BC/AC of the working budget, work programmes and the strategic plans, can be regarded as such guidance (but again: MB&BC/AC members do not represent the Council). Updates of legislation³⁷, by the Council/EP, can also be used to redefine the room for manoeuvre the agent has. In short, the control governance dimension is not well developed in the case of the EUIPO/CPVO. Given the low level of political salience of the IPRs involved, this situation may however present acceptable risks for the principal³⁸.

³⁷ Soft law (guidelines) can have the same function, but such soft law is made by the agent, and not by the principal.

³⁸ In the case of patents, and the EPO, the formal governance arrangements are largely identical to those of the CPVO, but here decisions are regularly taken that are contested politically. In that context, the Biotech Directive, limiting the patentability possibilities of certain biotechnological inventions, can be regarded as an intervention by the principal to control the agent.

Network management

If we look at the governance arrangements from the perspective of network management, they make much more sense. They arrange the main features of multi-level networks, with the EUIPO/CPVO as main hubs, and involvement of the main other actors in the system, including observers and user groups. However, three remarks can be made. First, if network management is the objective, then the MB&BC/AC should involve only representatives from those organizations that are actors in the management of the IPR systems, and should not be mixed. One can also argue against the basic rule for participation and decision-making, with one representative and one vote for each member, as some Member States are far more active in some IPR fields than others. The EC is also a player with considerable resources and interests, which is not reflected in the rules for participation and decision-making (especially not in the case of CPVO). Secondly, to take the previous argument a step further, network management is commonly not based upon formal decision-making rules and procedures, with decision-making powers in the hands of those actors that are active in the spokes of the network, upon proposal by the hub. Network decision-making is often consensual. This is reflected in how actual decision-making in the MB&BC/AC takes place: minutes of meetings, both for EUIPO and CPVO, almost always report such consensual decision-making³⁹. Thirdly, the involvement of (many) observers does not always makes sense, nor does having participants with only observer status in the first place. Either these are full-fledged actors within the network and should then be treated accordingly⁴⁰, or they represent stakeholders groups or societal fora that are not part of the management system, but should be addressed by means of accountability mechanisms.

Accountability

That brings us to the third dimension of agency governance: accountability. Apart from the general EU rules for transparency and access to documents, there are no legal arrangements for accountability of the EUIPO and CPVO. It is up to these organizations themselves to define fora and mechanisms for accountability. Here we run in the conflation that was mentioned earlier. The CPVO, for example, in its Strategic Plan 2017-2021) lists as their stakeholders the following groups: (a) organisations representing the interests of breeders or particular groups of breeders; (b) institutional actors such as the Administrative Council and the EU institutions that have defined governance roles; (c) other organisations with expertise or activities that relate to the CPVO's mission on a national, regional and international level; (d) individuals and organisations working directly for or with the

³⁹ In line with the findings by Font, 2018 for the OHIM, but contrary to these findings for CPVO.

⁴⁰ See along these lines, European Commission (2009), which argues that in the case of OHIM and CPVO, in the MB/AC, the interests of certain actors (EC, users) are represented in an unbalanced way.

CPVO such as the staff, contractors or cooperation partners (including the entrusted examination offices and experts), and (e) farmers, growers and consumers as users of what the protection scheme intends to stimulate: varietal progress. This thoroughly mixes up network participants, users, principals, other agents, and wider societal stakeholders. It creates confusion on what the accountability for/accountholders are, and what information the CPVO as accountgiver should provide. The EUIPO is even more fuzzy: in its Strategic Plan 2025 the term stakeholders is used often, but without any overview of who they are; accountability is referred to in correspondence with transparency and reporting, without identifying the accountholders and their needs. For both CPVO and EUIPO this fuzziness results in a multitude of information provided on websites and in various reports/plans⁴¹, that may comply with transparency requirements, but hardly add to accountability.

⁴¹ Busuioc & Rimkuté (2019) and Rimkuté (2019) have analysed how EU agencies deal with their reputations, which is related to but different from accountability. They expect decision-making agencies such as the EUIPO and the CPVO to emphasize legal-procedural and performative aspects of their functioning in their annual reports, as opposed to technical and moral aspects. Their findings, based on keyword searches in these annual reports, are however rather mixed. The EUIPO emphasizes performance and technical aspects, and the CPVO emphasizes technical aspects. Moral aspects are hardly addressed.

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